

ASCENT PROJECT

Summer school

CARBON STORAGE IN NET ZERO CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS

Day 3, May 28th, 2025

Teacher: Prof. Massimo Pizzol

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(full profile here: <https://vbn.aau.dk/en/persons/massimo>)

The lecture deals with an introductory theory of LCA, focusing on the specifics of the construction sector and the LCA regulations relevant to this sector. The lecture includes practical exercises with the LCA software (provided in advance by the lecturer), where participants work on a prepared case study dataset, analyse the impacts and solve specific tasks with the software.

Learning objectives:

Knowledge: after this module you will know about theoretical and computational framework of LCA, LCA guidelines relevant for the construction sector, and approaches for dynamic carbon accounting in LCA.

Skills: after this module you will be able to carry out LCA analysis using commercial software and databases, as well as to do basic dynamic carbon calculation with research tools.

Competences: after the module you will be able to assess the impact of net zero constructions products in a life cycle perspective.

Important! Preparation: before the course please

- Please watch the videos linked below on LCA.
- Check the readings listed below and read the two scientific papers.
- Install the software in advance, instructions below. **Important:** we won't have time to do this at the course! Do it before please. If you have problems, please write me in advance: massimo@plan.aau.dk

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Plan for the day (tentative):

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09:00-10:15 Questions and answers on the videos
Break
10:15: 12:00 Working in group on a case study: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- AAU prepares a case to work with in Simapro, it will be a full building.- Students work in groups, they import the data in the software and perform various tasks that are typical in LCA. A series of guiding questions will be provided.
Lunch
13:00 – 13:45 Presentation on dynamic approaches to LCA (Prof. Massimo Pizzol)
Break
14:00 – 15:30 Exercise: use some of the dynamic tools to calculate new emission factors for specific construction products, change the previous system to see differences.
Break
15:45 – 17:00 Group work: applying the life cycle perspective to your case
Closing the day

Software installation instructions

In the “LCA-Software” folder you will find:

- *SimaPro AAU Faculty Aalborg 012 (2025).pdf* → this is the software licence.
- *SimaPro quickstart guide (2025).doc* → This is how to install the Simapro Software
- *Simapro-installation-guide-with-conseq-SP9.6.0.1.pdf* → This is how to install the database that we will use in the course

The license is temporary for 2025 and is to be used only for educational purposes. Not for commercial ones.

Please install the software before the session. We will not use time on May 28th to solve software installation issues.

Ascent List of videos

Videos show how to structure and conduct a LCA, and how to implement LCA on the software [SimaPro](#) with database [ecoinvent](#).

The videos are on this page: please check the ones listed below:

<https://moutreach.science/2022/08/15/teaching-videos.html>

[2.1-MP-Functional-unit](#)

[2.2-MP-Product-system-flow-chart](#)

[3.1-MP-product-system-diagram-to-matrix](#)

[3.2-MP-understand-the-product-system-matrix](#)

[3.3-MP-multifunctional-activities-explained](#)

[3.4-MP-multifunctional-activities-matrix](#)

[4.1-MP-SimaPro-foreground-system](#)

[4.2-MP-SimaPro-background-system-described](#)

[4.3-MP-SimaPro-background-system-howtolink](#)

[4.4-MP-SimaPro-match-with-excel](#)

[5.1-MP-LCIA-theory](#)

[5.2-MP-LCIA-Simapro](#)

Essential list of readings and resources

- **A free book about LCA:** You don't need to read the entire free online textbook about LCA but the materials presented in the videos can be found in different chapters of this book: *Matthews et al. Life Cycle Assessment – Quantitative approaches for decisions that matter* <https://www.lcatextbook.com/>
- **A set of tools for dynamic accounting of forest products and climate impacts in LCA** taken from the *ALIGNED EU project* (mainly relevant for biobased products, but also beyond those):

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- Hamelin, L., Javourez, U., & Arbault, D. (2024). ALIGNED D1.2 Description of scientific methods (T1.3 Framework for Life Cycle Impact Assessment) (1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11126481>
- Lancz, K., Nørgaard Bollesen, K., & Pizzol, M. (2024). ALIGNED D1.2 Description of scientific methods (Task 1.2 Framework for foreground life cycle inventory of bio-based sectors - Dynamic carbon accounting) (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10843343>
- **A paper about the EPD system and how result differ across operators:** Konradsen, F., Hansen, K. S. H., Ghose, A., & Pizzol, M. (2024). Same product, different score: How methodological differences affect EPD results. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 29(2), 291–307. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-023-02246-x>
- **A paper showing an example of calculation of carbonation in concrete.** Elliot, T., H. Kouchaki-Penchah, V. Brial, A. Levasseur, and S.J. McLaren. 2024. Dynamic environmental payback of concrete due to carbonation over centuries. *Sustainable Production and Consumption* 51: 236–247. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2024.09.009>
- **A paper about using carbon capture and storage in a cement plant and the LCA of this.** Gallego Dávila, J., R. Sacchi, and M. Pizzol. 2023. Preconditions for achieving carbon neutrality in cement production through CCUS. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 425: 138935. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.138935>